

MECHANICAL RECYCLING OF GLASS FIBER REINFORCED WIND TURBINE BLADE COMPONENTS INTO PELLET-BASED FEEDSTOCKS FOR ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING

Dimitrij Seibert^{1,*}, Andrej Fehler¹, Jan Bürgener¹, Philipp Johst¹, Robert Böhm¹

¹Faculty of Engineering, HTWK Leipzig – University of Applied Sciences
Karl-Liebknecht-Straße 132, D-04277 Leipzig, Germany

Email: dimitrij.seibert@htwk-leipzig.de (corresponding author), andrej.fehler@htwk-leipzig.de, jan.buergener@htwk-leipzig.de, philipp.johst@htwk-leipzig.de, robert.boehm@htwk-leipzig.de

web page: <https://fing.htwk-leipzig.de/forschung-transfer/leichtbau-mit-verbundwerkstoffen/composite-circularity-lab>

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ABSTRACT

The rapid growth of the wind energy sector is expected to generate a significant amount of end-of-life (EoL) fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) waste as wind turbines reach their 20–25-year lifespan. By 2050, Europe is expected to accumulate around 7.6 million tons of FRP from decommissioned wind turbine blades (WTBs). Among the different disposal strategies, mechanical recycling is the most discussed due to its sustainability. This research investigates the reuse of mechanically recycled glass fiber reinforced polymers (GFRP) in 3D printing, specifically in the production of reinforced acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) pellets. Tensile samples with different fiber content are produced using a fused granulate fabrication (FGF) 3D printer and analyzed by X-ray micro-computed tomography (μ CT) and mechanical testing. The findings demonstrate the viability of incorporating recycled WTB materials into engineering thermoplastic composites, thereby enhancing their mechanical properties. Further research is needed to maximize the recycled content while meeting the performance criteria for demanding applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

The rapid expansion of the wind energy sector is expected to lead to a significant amount of end-of-life (EoL) fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) material stream in the coming years. This challenge arises as wind turbine blades (WTBs), which are primarily made of FRPs [1], reach the end of their initial 20 - 25 year life cycle [2]. According to Lahuerta *et al.* [3], approximately 7.6 million tons of FRP EoL WTB material mass will be generated in Europe by 2050. For Germany a total mass of EoL WTB of 689 kt is estimated [4].

Various strategies have been proposed and implemented in response to this impending material stream. The concept of different ‘R’s’ to manage EoL WTB materials, emphasizing reduction, reuse, recycling, recovery, and redesign [5]. According to Lund and Madsen [6], mechanical recycling is the most frequently discussed ‘R’-strategy in the literature for the management of EoL WTB materials. The recycling process includes a series of mechanical operations, such as cutting, shredding, grinding or crushing the WTB. These operations are intended to reduce the size of the resin and fibers or to separate them for further processing or direct use in secondary products [7]. Studies, such as those by Delvere *et al.* [8], have concluded that mechanical recycling is currently the most sustainable recycling technology for FRP WTBs, based on comprehensive sustainability criteria.

Mamanpush *et al.* [9] demonstrated the feasibility and potential of mechanically recycled WTB materials in the production of high-performance composites. For instance, recycled glass fiber reinforced polymers (rGFRPs) have been used in noise barriers [10], as a filler in concrete [11], and in sheet molding compounds [12]. Recent advancements have also explored the use of mechanically recycled fibers in 3D printing materials. In [13] it is demonstrated that recycled FRP could replace virgin fibers in additive manufacturing while maintaining mechanical integrity. Furthermore, several studies

by Rahimizadeh *et al.* ([14-17]) have investigated the integration of rGFRP materials with polylactic acid (PLA) in 3D printing, showing improvements in strength and modulus compared to neat PLA samples, despite some reductions in tensile strength and failure strain.

Building on recent advancements in the field of composite mechanical recycling, this research investigates the reuse of mechanically recycled GFRP materials in 3D-printing applications. The focus is on the optimized production of reinforced acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) composites incorporating rGFRP. Employing a pellet-based approach using fused granular fabrication (FGF) instead of filament-based fused deposition modeling (FDM) simplifies the printing process by reducing feedstock quality requirements. Furthermore, FGF and large-format additive manufacturing enable the direct reuse of recycled fiber-reinforced polymer (rFRP) granulate, making them highly effective for industrial-scale recycling and the scalable integration of composite EoL material into new large-scale applications [18, 19]. This approach aims to increase recycle incorporation while ensuring the mechanical integrity required for technical-grade applications.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 EoL WTB Material

For the present study, EoL WTB segments from an E40/6 wind turbine (Enercon, Germany) are selected as the source material. These segments are obtained through perpendicular cuts along the WTB length (see Figure 1a). The spar caps are cut out of the WTB segment through the utilization of a panel saw equipped with a diamond-tipped circular blade. The selection of these components is driven by their high glass fiber volume content and structural homogeneity, especially in comparison to the shear web and sandwich regions (see Figure 1b). The resulting spar cap material (see Figure 1c), which serves as the feedstock for subsequent mechanical size reduction, is composed of unidirectional glass fiber laminates embedded in an epoxy matrix. The glass fiber volume content of the spar cap material in an E40/6 WTB is estimated at approximately 57 % (calculated with a calcination process using a glass fiber density of $2.48 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ (measured with a pycnometer) and a matrix density of $1.2 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ [20]).

Figure 1: (a) Cutting section perpendicular to the length of the wind turbine blade (WTB); (b) Schematic cross-section of an E40/6 WTB (based on [21]); (c) Spar cap material used in this study for the shredding process.

2.2 Shredding and Sieving Process

To enable further processing, the previously prepared material is shredded using the GP20 Hybrid granulation system (3devo B.V., Utrecht, Netherlands), which combines a twin-shaft shredder and a rotary mill. The shredder features two counter-rotating shafts, each with seven blades bearing three teeth, while the milling stage includes a rotary cutter with three edges and a 3.4 mm sieve. The material is processed three times to ensure consistent fiber shortening and homogenization. The mixture is then dry-sieved using a sieve shaker (AS 200 Control, Retsch GmbH, Haan, Germany) with mesh sizes of 250 μm , 100 μm , and 63 μm . In the following, remaining material on the sieves (see Figure 2) is referred to as the "oversize fraction" (OF) in combination with the corresponding mesh size, e.g. OF>100. The OF>250 was further milled using a laboratory cutting mill (MF 10 basic Cutting Mill, IKA-Werke GmbH & Co. KG, Staufen, Germany) fitted with a 2 mm sieve to increase yield in the desired size ranges. For subsequent processing the OF>100 and OF>63 are selected.

Figure 2: Comparison of the oversize fractions.

2.3 Compounding and 3D-Printing

The OF>100 and OF>63 are compounded with virgin ABS (vABS) powder (MagnumTM 3513, INEOS Styrolution, Germany) with two different weight ratios. This results in five material variants: Neat vABS and four rGFRP compounds. ABS-rGF10/100 and ABS-rGF20/100 containing 10 wt% and 20 wt% rGFRP from the OF>100, respectively, as well as ABS-rGF10/63 and ABS-rGF20/63 containing 10 wt% and 20 wt% rGFRP from the OF>63 (Figure 3).

Dry mixing is followed by homogenization in a low-speed laboratory mixer until visual uniformity in fiber distribution and color is achieved. According to the specifications outlined in the MagnumTM 3513 datasheet, all materials are dried at a temperature of 80 °C for a duration of four hours in a convection oven. This procedure is conducted to remove residual moisture and prevent pore formation and surface defects caused by vapor expansion during extrusion.

The resulting compounds, along with vABS as reference, are extruded into continuous filaments using a Filament Maker ONE Composer 450 single-screw extruder (3devo, Netherlands). Parameters are chosen according to 3devo extrusion report for MagnumTM 3513 (heat zones h4-h1: 215, 225, 235, 245 °C with 2 mm nozzle diameter). The filaments are pelletized using an open-source pelletizer, printed out of vABS to minimize contamination.

Tensile samples are manufactured using a FGF 3D printer (Tumaker NX300 Modular, Tumaker S.L., Irun, Spain), equipped with a pellet extruder comprising two independently controlled heating zones and a 0.8 mm diameter hardened steel nozzle to mitigate abrasive wear from the rGFRP feedstocks. Tensile sample dimensions follow ISO 527-4 (Type 2) and are 250 × 25 × 2 mm (L × W × T). They are printed sequentially on a heated build plate set to 100 °C, with cooling fans deactivated. Slicing is performed using Simplify3D (Simplify3D LLC, Cincinnati, USA), applying a layer height of 0.2 mm, no outer perimeters, no top or bottom layers, and a 100 % infill with aligned pattern oriented parallel to the tensile load direction. Extrusion multipliers are calibrated individually for each compound to ensure closed layers and dimensional accuracy. Values range from 100 % for vABS to 118 % for ABS-rGF20/100. To provide an overview of the processing of the 3D-printed tensile samples, the procedure is summarized schematically in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Schematic representation of the processing route from EoL WTB to 3D-printed tensile samples.

2.4 Material Characterization of recyclates and tensile samples

In order to characterize the EoL WTB recyclates, the fiber mass and volume content of each OF is determined through calcination tests according to ISO 1172 and ISO 1183-1 (glass fiber density of $2.48 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ and matrix density of $1.2 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$). Particle size and shape are analyzed using the dynamic image analysis system QICPIC with the LIXELL wet dispersion module (Sympatec GmbH, Clausthal-Zellerfeld, Germany), following ISO 9276 and ISO 13322-2. Samples are dispersed in distilled water, homogenized by stirring, and treated with surfactant. Each sample is measured three times from two independent subsamples to ensure repeatability. Size distributions are evaluated as volume-based density $q_3^*(x)$. Calcinated fiber samples (OF>63 and OF>100) are described by fiber length (LEFI) and fiber diameter (DIFI). Particle shape is assessed via elongation and straightness. Volume is calculated using a cylindrical mode. Characterization of vABS is estimated by equal projected circle diameter (EQPC).

To characterize the tensile samples, X-ray micro-computed tomography (μCT) is conducted on one randomly chosen printed rGFRP sample per compound using a high-resolution system (Phoenix Nanotom M, Waygate Technologies GmbH, Wunstorf, Germany) to evaluate internal structure, porosity and fiber volume content. Scans are performed using *datos|x* software. Image processing and volumetric analysis are carried out using *VGSTUDIO MAX 2023.1* (Volume Graphics GmbH, Heidelberg, Germany). Fiber volume content and porosity are quantified via manual segmentation of a selected region of interest (ROI), located within the interior of the sample to exclude surface effects and ensure that surface roughness does not affect the measurements. Segmentation was based on the gray value histogram using the ISO50 threshold method, in accordance with the general guidelines of ISO 15708-3. The applied scan parameters are listed in Table 1.

Mechanical testing of the printed samples ($n=20$ for each variant) is conducted in accordance with ISO 527-1. Prior to testing, samples are conditioned under standard laboratory climate ($23 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 50 % relative humidity). A universal testing machine (Zwick Roell Z050, ZwickRoell GmbH & Co. KG, Germany) is used to determine tensile strength, Young's modulus, strain at break and tensile stress at break.

Table 1: Parameters used for μ CT-scans.

Parameter	Unit	Value
Tube voltage	kV	100
Tube current	μ A	110
Focus-detector-distance (FDD)	mm	290
Focus-object-distance (FOD)	mm	7.5
Voxel size	μ m	2.6
Number of projections	-	2500
Binning	-	1
Averaging	-	3

3 RESULTS

3.1 Characterization of recyclates

The mean fiber mass content of the OF>63 and OF>100 are 76.03 wt% and 78.36 wt%, respectively. This corresponds to fiber volume content of approximately 60.54 % and 63.67 %. The distribution curves of OF>63 and OF>100 are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Fiber length distribution density curves of the OF>63 and OF>100.

Both curves show right-skewed profiles with a broad spread of fiber lengths. OF>63 exhibits a wider distribution in the lower length range, with a gradual rise and a long tail extending toward higher lengths. The cumulative curve increases more steadily, indicating a relatively even spread of shorter and medium-length fibers. In contrast, OF>100 shows a steeper rise in the cumulative curve at longer lengths, reflecting a larger proportion of long fibers. Its density curve is shifted to the right, with a more pronounced peak at longer fiber lengths compared to OF>63.

The vABS sample shows a median EQPC of 147 μ m. OF>63 fibers range (Figure 4) from 40 to 852 μ m in length (x_{50} =263 μ m), while OF>100 fibers are longer overall, ranging from 106 to 926 μ m (x_{50} =371 μ m). The shift toward higher fiber lengths in OF>100 is also reflected in the cumulative distribution. Fiber diameters are similar in both samples, with median values of approximately 22 μ m. This indicates a higher proportion of long fibers in OF>100 compared to OF>63. The key parameters are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Key parameters for all analyzed materials.

Variant	Value	Unit	X ₁₀	X ₅₀	X ₉₀
vABS	EQPC	μm	45.76	147.42	345.56
OF>63	LEFI	μm	40.46	262.55	851.81
	DIFI	μm	15.59	22.01	28.07
OF>100	LEFI	μm	105.56	371.01	925.58
	DIFI	μm	17.18	22.42	28.31

3.2 Characterization of tensile samples

The μ CT analysis shows clear differences in internal structure, porosity and fiber volume content among the different compounds used for the tensile samples (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Cut out of cross-sections from the ROI in XY- and XZ-plane from the tensile samples of each compound.

For ABS-10rGF/63 and ABS-10rGF/100, the fiber volume content is approximately 5 vol%. ABS-20rGF/63 and ABS-20rGF/100 variants show an increased amount of approximately 9 vol%. A generally homogeneous fiber distribution is visible, with occasional fiber agglomerations. A preferred fiber orientation corresponding to the 3D printing paths is observed. Porosity within the ROIs ranges from 0.62 vol% to 1.58 vol%. The fiber volume content and porosity are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: μ CT-based quantification of fiber volume content and porosity in tensile samples of different compounds using ISO50 threshold values.

Parameter	Value	ABS-10rGF/63	ABS-20rGF/63	ABS-10rGF/100	ABS-20rGF/100
Fiber volume content	%	5.04	9.26	5.01	9.04
Porosity	%	1.04	1.58	0.62	0.91

The tensile tests results show improvements in stiffness and strength for all tested rGFRP samples compared to the vABS. Fracture occurs perpendicular to the loading axis in all variants (see Figure 6a). While vABS exhibits a distinct yield point, stress plateau, and extensive post-yield deformation, all rGFRP samples show a steeper slope with nearly linear elastic behavior up to failure with lower strain, lacking a visible yield point, except ABS-rGF10/63 (see Figure 6b and 6e). This finding suggests a shift in failure behavior due to the reinforcement with chopped fibers coming from EoL WTB spar cap material. An increase in mechanical properties from 10 wt% to 20 wt% compounds is observed. The greatest improvements in mechanical properties are observed for ABS-rGF20/63 with an increase of 101 % in Young's modulus and 27 % in tensile strength in comparison to vABS (see Figure 6c and Figure 6d). Tensile strain at failure reduces among all rGFRP compounds. Values decreased by 79 to 89 % compared to the reference. The increase in Young's modulus and tensile strength by increasing the fiber mass content from 10 wt% to 20 wt% is greater for OF>63 than for OF>100. Furthermore, the greatest dispersion was observed for ABS r20GF/100.

Figure 6: Mechanical testing of vABS and rGFRP samples: (a) tensile sample after testing; (b) mean stress–strain curves; (c) Young's modulus; (d) ultimate tensile strength; (e) stress at break.

The tensile test results are summarized in Table 4, which lists the engineering constants with mean values and standard deviations.

Table 4: Tensile test results: Youngs-Modulus (E_1), tensile strength (σ_1^{ult}), stress at break (σ_1^f) and strain at break (ε_1^f).

Engineering constant	Unit	vABS	ABS-rGF10/63	ABS-rGF20/63	ABS-rGF10/100	ABS-rGF20/100
E_1	MPa	2402±42	3367±61.4	4839±142	3734±74.3	4587±237
σ_1^{ult}	MPa	47.4±1.16	51.1±0.74	60.2±1.72	54.4±0.64	54.6±3.61
σ_1^f	MPa	35.6±1.57	46.6±1.57	60.2±1.72	54.2±1.02	54.6±3.62
ε_1^f	%	30.9±10	6.3±0.79	3.3±0.14	3.9±0.21	3.4±0.26

4 DISCUSSION

The incorporation of 10 wt% rGFRP into printed samples resulted in an enhancement in stiffness and strength, without compromising printability for either OF. The low porosity values and homogeneously distributed fibers in μ CT scans provide further evidence to support these findings. The use of vABS powder in the compounding process facilitates generally homogeneous fiber distribution, thereby ensuring consistent processing and mechanical behavior.

Conversely, combinations of elevated recycle content and coarser sieve fractions (OF>100) result in increased variability in mechanical properties and diminished surface quality. This phenomenon is likely attributable to impaired flow and printability, particularly when employing a 0.8 mm nozzle. Local printing defects and material inhomogeneities, including fiber agglomerations, have been identified as additional contributing factors to the observed deviations. These findings underscore the necessity of optimizing print parameters.

The measured fiber volume content of the rGFRP indicates that only small amounts of matrix material are lost during the mechanical recycling. In comparison to the initial spar cap material with approximately 57 vol%, the OF>63 and OF>100 show an increase of about 6.2 % and 11.7 %, respectively.

Fiber length and distribution have been identified as pivotal factors influencing both mechanical performance and processing behavior. The successful integration of short, mechanically recycled GFRP, which is often considered low-value residue, demonstrates its potential for use in circular material flows. The purely mechanical preparation route avoids pyrolysis or chemical treatment, thereby simplifying material recovery and enabling direct reuse in thermoplastic matrices.

The present study focuses on ABS in powder form and GFRP derived from EoL WTB spar cap material. While the method is applicable to other thermoplastics and WTB sections, components such as shear webs or sandwiches generally exhibit lower fiber content and higher levels of contaminants (e.g., balsa wood, polyurethane foam). These materials may necessitate supplementary separation or pretreatment procedures, such as air classification or density-based sorting, to yield recyclates suitable for further utilization. Furthermore, the mechanical test data and μ CT-based structural information may serve as a valuable basis for developing numerical simulation models of rGFRP-based components. These models have the potential to facilitate design optimization and material performance prediction in the field of additive manufacturing. In order to further validate these findings, it will be necessary to characterize additional parameters in subsequent studies. These additional parameters may include, but are not limited to, local fiber orientation, orientation distribution, and fiber-matrix interface quality.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The present study demonstrates the feasibility of mechanically recycled GFRP materials from EoL WTb spar caps into thermoplastic composites suitable for large-scale additive manufacturing. The applied process chain, which is entirely dependent on mechanical recycling steps such as cutting, shredding, milling, and sieving, enables the production of high-fiber-content recyclates. These recyclates are successfully compounded with ABS powder and processed via FGF.

These findings indicate that energy- and resource-intensive recycling methods, such as pyrolysis, are not necessary to produce compatible feedstocks for thermoplastic matrices. This contributes to the expansion of existing recycling strategies for WTbs beyond the practices of downcycling or incineration, thereby facilitating more circular material flows in accordance with established R-strategies. The developed process chain provides a scalable and transferable framework for the further utilization of fiber-rich WTb residues. To achieve the optimal utilization of this material, future research should prioritize increasing the recycled content while maintaining the processability and performance of the material.

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